

Quick Start Guide for Numerical Channel-Floodplain Routing Model (CFRMod) – as used in Pizzuto & Huffman (2024)

Download the following files into a new folder:

- “CFRMod.m”
- "create_non_uniform_storage_grid.m"

The CFRMod is set up to run a test in which a pulse of sediment is transported downstream through a series of reaches (whose geometry is detailed in Figure 2 of Pizzuto and Huffman, 2024) and cycled in and out of storage. Initially, no sediment is present within the channel or in floodplain storage except for the upstream input. The upstream input is then set to zero after the first timestep. The model provides data on the concentration of sediment in the channel, the volume of sediment in floodplain storage by age category, and the age categories. The following instructions detail the steps required to run the model and starts with the settings used to reproduce the results shown in Pizzuto & Huffman (2024).

Note that the spatial and temporal scale used in Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) and the regridding function make the model slow to run. To monitor progress, the model prints the timestep and regridding progress to the terminal screen.

1. Open the MATLAB script “CFRMod.m”
2. The model runs a regridding function to prevent the storage and age arrays from becoming too large and slowing down the model. The function "create_non_uniform_storage_grid.m" is called by the model and should be located in the same folder in which the model MATLAB script is stored. This function is called on Line 101 of CFRMod.m.
3. We can first set how many timesteps will pass before the regridding function will run. This is done by adjusting the variable “regridtime”. Pizzuto and Huffman (2024) use a “regridtime” value of 1000, meaning that after 1000 timesteps have passed, the data in storage will be regridded, and the “regridtime” count will start over. Additionally, the regridding function requires the user to specify the size the array will be regridded to using the variable “regridnum”. Huffman & Pizzuto (2024) use a “regridnum” value of 100, meaning that after “regridtime” is reached, the storage and age arrays are regridded from a length of 1000 down to 100 (see Lines 15-16 of CFRMod.m).
4. The model operates on a length of stream channel divided into a series of smaller reaches defined by the spatial step “dx_DL”. Set the spatial step, dx_DL (should be a small value to prevent numerical instability; Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) use 0.0001) and the maximum length of the channel (set by defining the end of the array x, Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) use 20). (see Lines 21-22 of CFRMod.m).
5. The model will run for a specified number of timesteps defined by the maximum run time, tmax, and the size of the timestep, dt_DL. Set timestep, dt_DL (should be a small value to prevent numerical instability; Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) use 0.0001), and the total time the model will

run for, t_{max} (Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) use a value of 5). Step 8 outlines how data can be pulled for shorter runtimes (see Lines 26-27 of CFRMod.m).

6. Recall that this model is testing the movement of an initial sediment pulse from the upstream end. This is done by setting the concentration at the upstream-most node ($Cs_DL(1,1)$). Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) use $1/dx_DL$. All other Cs_DL values are initially zero. These values are implemented in Lines 32-33 of CFRMod.m.
7. Pizzuto & Huffman demonstrate two erosion scenarios. One assumes that erosion is dependent on the age of the stored sediment and follows a modified power function calibrated to mid-Atlantic chronostratigraphic data developed by Pizzuto (2023), while the other is age-independent, where a constant fraction is removed from storage regardless of age. If using the variable erosion by age function the erosion constants will remain as shown in lines 79-81. If erosion is constant regardless of age lines 79-81 must be commented out (using the MATLAB comment character % in the first column) and line 82 must be uncommented and set equal to the desired fraction removed from all age categories.
8. The model is set up to export results at selected times. Adjust when and where the data will be saved using lines 119-133. The model is set to reproduce the data present in Pizzuto & Huffman (2024) saving data at time = 0.1, 2, and 5. The file names and variables saved can be adjusted in line 120, 127, and 130 for the three times selected. Default variables that are saved are the spatial grid (x), the concentration in the channel (Cs_DL), the stored sediment volume (Old_Stored_DL), and the contact age (Old_TBound). The concentration vs distance is also plotted here for each time selected.
9. The model is now ready to run. Line 90 prints the iteration the model is on to the command window and is helpful for tracking progress. If the model is in the process of running the regridding function, line 99 prints "REGRIDDING" to the command window.
10. Model Outputs will be stored wherever specified in step 8.

References:

Pizzuto, J., & Huffman, M.E., (2024). Compact Models Quantify the Impact of Floodplain Storage on Sediment Delivery Timescales and Restoration Efficiency. *Water Resources Research (Submitted)*.

Pizzuto, J. (2023). A model for mid-Holocene-Present U.S. mid-Atlantic Piedmont river corridor sediment budgets fit to stratigraphic data. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 128, e2023JF007299. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023JF007299>.